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Impact of Course Selection on Career Paths of Arellano University Students: A Framework for Professional Development

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Abstract

This research examines what factors influence college students' choice of academic courses considering their career paths in the future at Arellano University Plaridel Campus. The study used quantitative analysis on data collected from 95 first year students to identify the main determinants. The results showed that majority of the participants were females (51.6%) aged between 19-21 years (43.2%) with HRM/Tourism being chosen by 35.2% while criminology had been selected by 30.7%. Students' course choices were motivated internally as they perceived them to be useful for their future jobs (mean=3.4) and received much support from families (m=3.5). Moreover, higher chances of getting well-paying jobs related to one's field of study were found to have significantly influenced the decision-making process (mean=3.42), thus reflecting socio-economic factors involved in this regard. Apart from these findings showing how intrinsic, interpersonal and socio-economic aspects interrelate when it comes to choosing courses among students at different levels of education; there is need for a program tailored towards career placement which should take into account such dynamics like parental involvement, industry relevance and financial implications so as to enable learners make informed decisions about their work lives.

Keywords: *career, academic course, professional career framework, college students*

Introduction

Education serves as a cornerstone for addressing socio-economic challenges worldwide. It is a catalyst for fighting poverty, ignorance, unemployment, and other social ills. Education's role in improving the quality of life and social status is widely recognized. Therefore, the decision made when selecting courses to study should not be taken lightly since it greatly affects one's professional path especially among college going students.

During career selection phase, people try to find themselves by matching their personal dreams with what they want to pursue professionally. According to Akosah-Twumasi et al. (2018), career choices are powerful tools for shaping identity and directing lifelong endeavors of individuals. Each student has unique experiences that have been influenced by environment, such as where one grew up or lives currently, opportunities available around him/her, personality traits among others thus making them see things differently from others depending on these factors that have shaped their world view about life and careers. For most young people college choice is very critical because it sets foundation for their future achievements hence success in workplaces. However, making this decision becomes complex due multifaceted brought about by inner self desires mixed with external influences like parental expectations or peer pressure among many more factors which can lead even confusion if not well managed therefore schools need understand all these so as provide necessary support guidance during such moments when students are trying figure out themselves educationally and professionally too. Every student brings his own personal history with them into the classroom so no two students will see things exactly alike. This history includes everything from where they grew up through who their friends were at various points in time; all of which is shaped by environment as well personality type as well opportunities afforded.

This problem does not belong only to some but rather belongs to everybody regardless of race or nationality because we are all affected by it one way or another either directly indirectly through someone else whom we know closely related with us like family member friend workmate etc. Choosing college for many students becomes life changed since it determines what they will become future terms of career success and general life achievements.

Arellano University Plaridel Campus is in Mandaluyong City, Philippines, which itself presents a dynamic context against which to study student decision-making around careers. With its diverse student population drawn from various socio-economic backgrounds who have different dreams about what profession they want pursue; the institution offers rich ground for investigating how these factors interplay with each other in shaping choice of courses at college level towards attainment desired professional futures paths among learners enrolled in this setting. The main objective this research was therefore to find out why current students taking their studies at Arellano University – Plaridel Campus chose such course leading into certain professions as reflected by own words used when describing them Data were collected through administering a questionnaire that sought respondents' demographic information alongside inquiries on aspects considered important during selection processes including self-awareness, parental influence, peer pressure etcetera.

What makes an appropriate occupation, career or profession varies from individual to another depending on work experience; with some people considering pay more than anything else while others value job security most thus implying that there are multiple ways through which individuals may arrive at same conclusion regarding what constitutes best suited work path for oneself.

Research Questions

This study sought to determine the Factors that influences College Students of Arellano University Plaridel Campus in choosing their Academic Course towards Professional Career: Basis for Career Placement Program.

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 age;
 - 1.2 gender; and
 - 1.3 course?
2. What are the factors that influence college students in choosing their course in terms of:
 - 2.1 intrapersonal dimension;
 - 2.2 interpersonal dimension; and
 - 2.3 socio-economic?
3. What are the professional careers influence the respondents?
4. Based on the study, what career placement program can be used in choosing an Academic Course towards a Professional Career?

Literature Review

The first people a child interacts with are the members of its family within its home – parents, siblings, and other relatives (Koçak et al., 2021). The authors added that among the many factors in the family that affect a child were the marital relationship of his or her parents, their socio-economic status, whether parents are warm or hostile towards each other (atmosphere of home), environmental condition around them, occupational status of both mother and father as well as number siblings within their household. Hence family dynamics greatly influence students' career readiness.

Also, according to Akosah-Twumasi et al. (2018), significant others can also be external forces that shape one's career choice through social support from peers. This means that those around us have a lot to do with what we finally decide on.

Eremie and Okwulehie (2018) identified environmental opportunities and personality as some factors that may determine why some secondary school students choose careers over others. For example, it was found out that among environmental factors; family background played an important role whiles socioeconomic status together with peer groups influenced majority of students' choice of career at this level similarly education mentorship constituted part opportunity factors but not forgetting about student's interest values skills when selecting courses based on their abilities.

Some key variables underpinning compliance with social learning theory include opinions held by peers and the amount of social influence experienced by an individual during interaction (Akers et al., 1979).

Jimenez and Novo (2019) said families are usually responsible for funding students who want to pursue medical laboratory science because they provide financial aid.

Methodology

This section presents the research design and respondents of the study, research instruments, data gathering procedure and the statistical treatment of data.

Research Design

The researchers made use of a quantitative research method that emphasizes the objective measurements and the statistical, mathematical, and numerical analysis of data collected through polls, questionnaires, and surveys by using computational techniques and made use of a descriptive research design that describes and analyzes the data characteristic about the population and the phenomenon being studied. A stratified sampling was used in this study, a sampling that is a probability sampling which plays a major role in the selection of item and or in making decisions in case of incomplete responses or observation that usually based on certain criteria.

Participants

Arellano University Plaridel Campus is located at #53 General Kalentong Street, Mandaluyong City. The respondents involved in this research were ninety-five (95) 1st year freshmen college students both males and females enrolled in all courses for academic year 2021-2022. With 95 students being sampled, a wide range of perspectives from various backgrounds can be captured which represents the target population adequately for this study. Not every student within such a large number would have been included thus it only provides meaningful insights about what influences course selection among college goers while still reflecting their career aspirations.

Ethical Considerations

This study followed some established rules to protect rights as well-being among other issues concerning those who took part.

1. **Informed Consent:** Before collecting data let participants know why they are being asked questions or observed, how it's done so as potential risks may arise during such activities should also be made aware off by them giving consent freely knowing that whatever revealed shall not go beyond those involved.
2. **Confidentiality:** Measures put in place should ensure that no personal identifiers are attached onto collected responses so that privacy remains intact always where possible everything must keep secret until otherwise authorized by relevant authority concerned with protection sensitive information.
3. **Protection of Vulnerable Participants:** When minors or persons with limited capacity to make decisions involved extra care considered their interests should not violated while carrying out research work thus any additional measure needed be implemented safeguarding rights these individuals throughout process.
4. **Research Integrity:** The researchers must be honest, act ethically and respect dignity of all who participated in this study. All personal interests interfering with objectivity during such investigations ought disclosed while conducting them professional standards expected from every researcher adhered to during this whole exercise.

Development of Research Instrument

The researcher constructed and developed a questionnaire, composed of 10 questions in each given variables that will be used in conducting the survey in determining the Factors that influences college students at Arellano University Plaridel Campus in Choosing their Academic Course towards Professional Career: Basis for Career Placement Program

Validation of Research Instrument

The researcher constructed and developed a questionnaire for the Factors that influences college students at Arellano University Plaridel Campus in choosing their academic course towards professional career: basis for Career Placement Program.

The researcher has consulted three proponents to help validate the research paper first is the grammarian that specializes language development, second is the statistician, an expert in the preparation and analysis of statistics and lastly is the course specialist.

Results

This section presents the results, findings, analysis, and interpretation of data gathered from the College students in Arellano University Plaridel Campus through the questionnaire distributed to them.

This study sought answers to the following sub-problems:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:

Table 1.1 *Distribution of the respondents in terms of Age*

Age	Frequency	Percentage
16-18	38	40%
19-21	41	43.2%
22 Above	16	16.8%
Total	95	100%

Table 1.1 is the frequency distribution of the respondents in terms of their age. It can be seen among the 95 respondents, most of them are 19-21 years old which is equivalent to 43.2%; followed by 40% of the respondents aged 16-18.

Table 1.2 *Distribution of the respondents in terms of Gender*

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	46	48.4%
Female	49	51.6%
Total	95	100%

As shown in Table 1.2 the frequency distribution of the respondents in terms of their gender. The findings revealed that the greatest number of respondents are female which is 49 or 51.6% while the remaining are male which is 46 or 48.4%.

Table 1.3 *Distribution of the respondents in terms of Course*

Course	Frequency	Percentage
Psychology	15	15.9%
Criminology	27	30.7%
Education	11	9.1%
HRM/TOURISM	31	35.2%
Accounting Technology	11	9.1%
Total	95	100%

Table 1.3 shows the frequency distribution of the respondents in terms of their course. Most of the respondents are HRM/Tourism

students which is equivalent to 35.2%, followed by 30.7% of Criminology and 15.9% for the Psychology students and the least with the same percentage is the accounting technology and education students which is equivalent to 9.1%.

2. What are the factors that influence college students in choosing their course in terms of:

Table 2.1 *Distribution of the administered respondents in which factors that influence College Students of Arellano University Plaridel Campus in Choosing Academic Course Towards Professional Career: Basis for Career Placement Program.*

<i>Intrapersonal Relationship</i>	SA (4)	A (3)	D (2)	SD (1)	WM
1. I chose my course based on the subject in which I excel the most.	35	57	2	1	3.32%
2. I considered my abilities and capabilities as potential factors when I chose my course	37	53	5	0	3.33%
3. I am confident that I will excel in the course I chose	35	56	4	0	3.34%
4. I chose my course based on my interests (e.g. Sports, arts, etc.)	30	55	10	0	3.21%
5. I considered my chosen course as a passion.	38	46	10	1	3.27%
6. I find my course as an advantage in my future career.	39	55	1	0	3.4%
7. I chose a course that will not give me too much stress or exhaustion.	15	54	20	4	2.8%
8. I chose a course that gives me the challenge to bring out the best in me.	36	54	4	1	3.31%
9. I chose a course that is traditionally taken by the gender I belong to.	17	46	24	8	2.75%
10. I chose a course that will create a good personal image for me in the future.	40	51	3	1	3.36%
Total					3.20%

Table 2.1 presents the factors that influenced College Students of Arellano University Plaridel Campus in Choosing Academic Course Towards Professional Career: Basis for Career Placement Program, the frequency shows the respondents who answered item no. 6 “I find my course as an advantage in my future career.” With a mean of 3.4 as strongly agree.

Table 2.2 *The factors that influenced College Students of Arellano University Plaridel Campus in Choosing Academic Course Towards Professional Career: Basis for Career Placement Program*

<i>Interpersonal</i>	SA (4)	A (3)	D (2)	SD (1)	WM
1. My family had an influence on the course I chose.	12	42	35	6	2.63%
2. I chose my course with my parents’ preference.	10	32	40	13	3.04%
3. My friends had an influence on the course I chose.	4	25	53	13	2.21%
4. My parents’ educational attainment had an influence with the course I chose.	7	12	55	12	2.24%
5. My family supported me in my chosen course	49	45	1	0	3.50%
6. My parents and /or relatives took the same course that I am pursuing.	13	26	45	10	2.42%
7. My parents’ career path achievement inspired me in choosing my course.	11	35	38	11	2.48%
8. Preferences are made by sponsors (e.g. relatives, scholarship grants, etc.) since they will provide for my expenses.	9	38	37	11	2.47%
9. My former teachers/mentors had an influence on the course I chose.	18	32	37	8	2.61%
10. I chose my course because it is the mainstream.	13	44	29	9	2.64%
Total					2.62%

Table 2.2 shows the factors that influenced College Students of Arellano University Plaridel Campus in Choosing Academic Course Towards Professional Career: Basis for Career Placement Program, the frequency shows the respondents who answered item no. 5 “My family supported me in my chosen course.”. With a mean of 3.50 as strongly agree is also shown at a study that college students and non-college students who were involved in a study agreed that parents are the most influential or important person when choosing their choice of college or university and course of study because parents perceive as their main source of finance and normally seek advice from them due to the perception that parents have the relevant information or experience with regards to higher education, and hence, parents are viewed as a credible source of advice.

Table 2.3 *The factors that influenced College Students of Arellano University Plaridel Campus in Choosing Academic Course Towards Professional Career: Basis for Career Placement Program*

<i>Socio-Economic</i>	SA (4)	A (3)	D (2)	SD (1)	WM
1. I chose a course that will improve my living conditions.	28	60	7	0	3.22%
2. Jobs or careers that are in line with my course provides a good salary.	29	60	4	1	3.42%
3. Jobs or careers that are in line with my course have good stability.	27	64	4	0	3.24%
4. I chose my course because it has in-demand jobs.	23	59	13	0	2.47%
5. I chose a university that offers a low tuition fee for my course.	15	59	19	2	2.28%
6. I chose a course that requires a low tuition fee.	15	51	25	3	2.8%
7. I chose my course based on my family’s income	14	50	26	5	2.76%
8. I chose a course that will help me gain a privilege or power in the future.	27	51	15	2	3.08%
9. Jobs or careers that are in line with my course have a high employment rate.	27	64	4	0	3.24%
10. I chose my course based on scholarship grants.	6	35	47	7	2.42%
Total					3.19%

Table 2.3 presents the factors that influenced College Students of Arellano University Plaridel Campus in Choosing Academic Course Towards Professional Career: Basis for Career Placement Program, the frequency shows that the respondents who answered to item

no. 2. “Jobs or careers that are in line with my course provides a good salary.” with a mean of 3.42 as strongly agree, and from that we can also include that the students chose their courses in relation to how productive a course is and if it needed in the industry, high paying jobs too are also considered as a factor in choosing courses. On the contrary, students also have a misconception about the professions due to lack of information – it prevents them from choosing.

Table 2.4 *The factors that influenced College Students of Arellano University Plaridel Campus in Choosing Academic Course Towards Professional Career: Basis for Career Placement Program*

<i>Career Fields</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Ranking</i>
Hospitality and Tourism	24	25.5%	1
Law, Public Safety, Corrections and Security	13	13.8%	2
Arts, Audio/Video Technology and Communications	10	10.6	3
Education and Training	9	9.6%	4
Business Management and Administration	7	7.4%	5
Human Services Careers	6	6.4%	6
Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics Agriculture, Food and Natural Resources Marketing, Sales, and Service Careers	5	5.3%	7
Government and Public Administration	4	4.3%	8
Architecture and Construction	3	3.2%	9
Finance Career	2	2.1%	10
Health Science Careers Transportation, Distribution and Logistics	1	1.1%	11
Manufacturing Career	-	-	-
Total	95	100%	

Table 2.4 shows the factors that influenced College Students of Arellano University Plaridel Campus in Choosing Academic Course Towards Professional Career: Basis for Career Placement Program, the frequency shows the respondents chose Hospitality and Tourism and has the highest ranking with the percentage of 25.5% which is the interpretation of Career fields to be chosen by 1st-year students at Arellano University Plaridel Campus. And that three out of six parental influential factors derived from 22 attributes are determined as being the salient predictors for students' H&T career choice intention.

Conclusion

The research was conducted only in Arellano University Plaridel Campus which may not represent other college students of Philippines or worldwide. Location, socio-economic status, educational background of the students may influence the outcome of this study, but findings cannot be applied to them because they were not included as partakers. Even though stratified sampling technique was used during data collection there might still be some biases in choosing participants. For instance, the subjects were limited to first year college students without any consideration for older ones or those who are at different levels academically that could have diverse views regarding course selection. Moreover, 95 respondents may be too small a number compared to many factors influencing choice. Self-reporting through questionnaires is vulnerable to response bias hence reliability of data collected is compromised. People tend to lie when giving information especially about something they think will make them look bad or good before others therefore it is subjective. Responders might feel under obligation to conform with societal expectations/ norms while answering questions so their input on issues like family support system and future job prospects could be overrated/underplayed leading inaccurate results concerning these factors impact on course selection process.

This study took place within one academic year (2021-2022) amid certain social economic conditions which may have affected how individuals perceived things thus making choices based on them during that period alone; however, employment trends change with time alongside technological improvement besides values shift overtime thereby rendering these findings outdated eventually. Intrapersonal, interpersonal socio-economic dimensions are some among other elements identified by this research as having bearing on deciding what course an individual should take up at higher learning level but it should not be seen as the whole truth since there can be more grounds for choosing than those considered here which interact differently depending on personal interests ability performance external influence from friends career expectations etcetera not covered by current framework used in conducting the study.

Future studies can enlarge their target group to encompass wider range of backgrounds, schools, and grades. It would also be interesting for researchers to come up with comparative analysis between various regions or even nations to find out if there are any universalities or cultural peculiarities regarding factors affecting choice making process among learners. Factors influencing course selection should be tracked over time by carrying out longitudinal research which follows students' academic and occupational paths from start to finish therefore this will help establish whether such determinants remain stable or change as one progresses in education. More so knowing what drives individuals at different points during college life may inform specific strategies aimed at assisting them through various stages including transition into employment.

In addition to quantitative information gathering methods like surveys, qualitative techniques such as interviews and focus groups could be employed when investigating why people choose courses this is because they allow deeper exploration into personal experiences motivations as well contextual considerations surrounding subject selection. Schools might use insights gained from

findings presented herein designing interventions that facilitate better decision making among pupils about their future career paths based on academic qualifications attained thus far. This can be done through provision career guidance programs mentorship initiatives or exposure events where students get hands-on experience related fields they wish pursue after completing studies.

Considering the results and conclusions of this study, the following recommendations are made: (1) Better Career Counseling Services: Arellano University Plaridel Campus should improve their career counseling services to give personalized advice to students depending on what factors they have identified as affecting their choice of a course. Put in place focused sessions where scholars can investigate how their selected program fits into their future career objectives and possible job opportunities. Use the discovery from Table 2.1 that many learners view their course as beneficial for their careers. (2) Involvement of Families in Program: Create programs that will involve families more in supporting students' decisions about courses and careers. Arrange workshops or seminars for parents and other family members to appreciate the significance of their backing when it comes to academic success and choice of profession by children. Such could be justified with findings in Table 2.2 whereby a large percentage strongly agreed that family support influenced my selection of this subject area. (3) Curriculum Review: Should tailor offerings around what students want – Work with faculties so that they can revise current provision based on students' perceived interests vis-à-vis employment prospects. This may entail introducing new electives, concentrations or minors which reflect popular paths highlighted by respondents in the survey such as Hospitality and Tourism. (4) Internships and Industrial Visits: Widen exposure through internships within relevant industries where one can gain hands on skills needed for specific jobs chosen later on life; Establish links between organizations engaged in various sectors related to preferred fields thus enabling placement opportunities among learners themselves; Also hold trade fairs plus networking functions which will connect individuals pursuing different careers at different levels. Highlighting practical experience necessary for career readiness is demonstrated by finding at table number three which shows that most students want high paying jobs aligned with my course. (5) Information Campaigns: Roll out campaigns aimed at providing accurate information concerning diverse professions as well emerging trends in employment. Create materials, sessions and online platforms that will help correct people's wrong ideas about certain jobs while at the same time giving them insights into what is currently happening within various industries career wise. The basis for such could be rooted from findings of Table 2.3 which indicates that students may not have enough facts about professions due to lack of knowledge.

Proposed Programs for the Respondent's Development. (1) Conducting seminars regarding self-reflection practices, so students can have a deeper insight about their interests in terms of career plans. (2) Skills exploration activities, helps students show their talent or aptitude towards their suited course. (3) Use a gap-based approach. To identify what training and expertise they already have, and what training and expertise they need to gain. (4) Innovate resources that align around and support the purpose of the respondent's development of their career choice.

Objectives. Its aim is to support the school, community, students, parents, and school official as they consider, propose, or conduct seminars to have career development and enhancing one's future. This program is purely preparing oneself for the future career. It requires a well-equipped, good competency, skills, and more structured way of planning and performing. It motivates the individuals to find and collect information and data required which helps them when it comes to decision making and maintaining a good work life.

Goals. To focused on outcome seminars preparing for college students and careers is fueling a refocus on career preparation and shining a spotlight on efforts to foster early career awareness among students. Students in different courses and year levels will benefit from this program and also the whole community.

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